
FVON INSTRUMENT INTERCOMPARISON EXPERIMENTS PHASE 1-CRUISE REPORTS

**CNR
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MARINE

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1. Introduction

1.1 Rationale

The Fishing Vessel Ocean Observing Network ¹ (FVON) is an international, interdisciplinary group dedicated to advancing ocean observing in partnership with the global fishing industry (Van Vranken et al. 2023). Fishing vessels provide a unique opportunity to collect oceanographic data, offering valuable insights into our coastal seas and filling in data gaps (Van Vranken et al. 2020). Because global fishing fleets are diverse in terms of methods, practices, and cultural contexts, coordinated frameworks are essential to ensure consistency, quality, and interoperability of the data collected. To manage the wide range of data and enhance fishing-vessel-based ocean observations globally, FVON establishes best practices, facilitates the adoption of observation technologies, and maximizes the value of ocean data. Through global collaboration, FVON generates rigorous, cost-effective ocean data that contributes to a transformative shift in understanding the changing oceans and supports sustainable decision-making.

A central component of this effort is the development and dissemination of operational best practices, including guidelines on the optimal pairing of instruments and fishing gear, together with appropriate deployment configurations based on specific regional needs worldwide. Given the variety of instruments used for the collection of oceanographic variables across FVON programs and the need to ensure alignment with oceanographic class instrument standards, FVON is conducting intercomparison studies to increase transparency around sensor and instrument development needs, strengthen understanding of characteristics and performance, and ultimately improve data quality.

Intercomparison studies are conducted using a participatory and peer-reviewed methodology in three coordinated steps: (1) conducting a survey of commercial instrument options suitable for deployment on fishing gear while capable of producing data comparable to traditional oceanographic systems; (2) defining comparison protocols informed by partner expertise and established practices; and (3) designing and performing a series of intercomparison experiments to identify best practices for operational use under varying environmental and fishery conditions.

This process not only provides valuable feedback to manufacturers, helping them improve their systems and define their market position, but also plays a critical role in ensuring that data meets scientific and operational needs. Furthermore, this process can enrich the metadata that accompanies the data collected by the instruments. This helps ensure that data is reliable and useful to end users, supporting more informed decision making and more effective network planning.

Initially, a dedicated FVON team of experts focused on intercomparisons of temperature profiling instruments, with a secondary emphasis on salinity

¹ <https://fvon.org/>

measurements. The adopted testing protocol was split into different Phases (see details in section 1.2).

The present report focuses on the operational outcomes of Phase 1 intercomparison activities, including deployment feasibility, data acquisition and transmission, power and memory constraints, and ease of use under realistic field conditions. A separate companion documentation provides a detailed analytical evaluation of temperature (and, where applicable salinity) performance relative to tested instruments.

These reports are also useful to demonstrate that fishing-vessel-based observing systems within FVON can deliver data of comparable quality to established oceanographic platforms. At the same time, this work seeks to identify operational constraints and technology gaps that must be addressed to enable scalable, long-term deployments across diverse fisheries and regions. By synthesizing results across multiple test sites, this report is intended to inform Phase 2 instrument selection, the development of FVON best practices, and ongoing engagement with sensor manufacturers regarding innovation priorities.

1.2 Protocol for Testing

Under the intention of a participatory approach, regular communication was maintained between the FVON community and manufacturers of instruments suitable for this application. In June 2024, a flyer was produced to explain the intent of the intercomparison study and to solicit participation of relevant and interested technology providers. These providers were asked to collaborate by providing the instruments to be tested free of charge and offering regular feedback on the correct use of the instruments.

The FVON Instrument Intercomparison Study Task Team 2 developed an intercalibration protocol which was formally approved by the FVON Steering Committee in October 2024, based on the experience previously acquired by partners on the validation of instruments designed to be used on fishing gears (e.g. Martinelli et al., 2016, 2017, 2023). The protocol was designed to provide a common framework for field testing procedures that could both simulate the use of compact sensors in fisheries and ensure consistency across intercomparison experiments. The Task Team carried out tests in different geographical areas under diverse environmental conditions, incorporating feedback from multiple crews while using a range of instrument types and brands, including also some technologies not specifically designed for fishing-vessel-based observing.

The intercalibration protocol is based on comparing field measurements collected from the instruments during oceanographic cruises against data from a commercial, oceanographic-class Conductivity, Temperature, Depth (CTD) instrument. Possible bias from different acquisition speeds is mitigated by conducting simultaneous profiling (Fig. 1) and focusing on datasets from stable depth intervals. The duration of the stops

² <https://www.fvon.org/about-us/>
<https://www.coastpredict.org/fishing-vessel-ocean-observing-network-ocean-decade-id-46-5/>

was designed to ensure the most reliable data collection and the logging of a sufficient amount of data to analyze considering that some sensors may take a few seconds to stabilize at various depths.

In addition to measuring depth, temperature, and other relevant variables, the protocol also verified each instrument's data recovery and transmission systems. It established standard procedures to assess measurement accuracy and define any possible offsets for the sensors and instruments tested.

The FVON team agreed to begin testing in three geographical locations: Italy, USA, and Japan. It was therefore necessary to arrange logistics to have the instruments and reference CTDs available in each testing location before the planned testing cruises, as outlined in Phase 0 below. The study then progressed through controlled profiling tests (Phase 1). Operational trials on fishing gear will follow (Phase 2). More details on each progressive phase of the study are outlined below. The present report focuses on Phases 0, 1.1, and 1.2, while Phase 1.3 is reported in separate documentation (see below for additional details).

Phase 0:

- Companies ship instruments directly to the testing site and participate in the technicalities of deployment design (e.g., instrument positioning and orientation, deployment speed).
- Staff involved in the testing activity familiarize themselves with the instrument settings (e.g., selection of time stamps other than UTC, settings for recording cycles) and the data collection mechanisms (e.g., activation limits based on time or depth, minimum data recording interval, response times, accuracy declared by the manufacturer).
- Prior to field deployment, teams to review the instruction manuals provided by the companies, become familiar with the instrument activation mechanisms and associated software for setting or downloading data, and test the instruments not only in the laboratory but also in confined environments such as ports.

Phase 1:

Phase 1.1: simultaneous profiling to simulate fishing conditions (Figure 1):

- mount instruments on a traditional CTD frame (possibly with depth detector at the same height as the CTD one, otherwise the height difference should be documented as it should be used to correct the data for subsequent analyses),
- deploy at fixed speeds (max speed 1 m/s).
- stop at different depths during the downcast/upcast (ideally 4 depth levels depending on the maximum, for 3-5 minutes each).

Phase 1.2: reporting:

- based on the field tests carried out, document aspects such as data acquisition and transmission, power and memory constraints, and ease of use under realistic field conditions,
- continuously interact with instrument producers to communicate results, clarify technical questions, and report any concerns.

Phase 1.3: data analysis:

- review obtained datasets and carry out formal analyses,
- evaluate instruments characteristics and performance to define suitability for the purpose and best operational conditions (e.g. discriminate between instruments capable of delivering full water-column profiles and those suitable only for bottom measurements, determine the type of fishing gear on which they can be mounted etc.).

Phase 2:

- based on the results and evaluation carried out in Phase 1, select instruments suitable for direct use on fishing gears according to FVON's operational objectives,
- test various instruments simultaneously on the same fishing gear to enable direct comparison under real fishing conditions, evaluate operational aspects such as instrument protection need and possible issues as fouling etc.,
- define best operational conditions for each instrument type, including optimal mounting conditions (e.g. how to position the instrument to ensure correct flow), deployment speeds, handling procedures, and performance expectations under routine fishing operations.

The preliminary results obtained in each region involved in Phase 1 of the intercomparison study were sent to manufacturers for feedback in July 2025.

A detailed R script³ was also produced in order to carry out further analyses on the collected data in a transparent and systematic manner (Phase 1.3). File formats were homogenized and data were plotted. Furthermore, the team obtained descriptive statistics to check for accuracy and account for occurring offsets toward the reference CTD at different depths (see specific document for detailed results).

The execution of the intercomparison tests was shared through different social media channels to disseminate the activities to the scientific community and increase engagement. The providers of the instruments which are currently used by FVON programs were publicly acknowledged as partners on social media and are referenced on the FVON website as technology providers⁴.

³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19372978>

⁴ <https://www.fvon.org/partners/>

Sensor Intercalibration Protocol

Phase 1: simultaneous profiling!

Simulation of fishing conditions to test accuracy, define offsets etc.:

- sensors mounted on a traditional CTD frame (possibly same height as the depth detector),
- deployed at fixed speeds (max speed 1m/s),
- with stops at different depths during the downcast/upcast (e.g. 4 depth levels depending on the maximum depth, for 3-5 minutes each).

Figure 1. Schematic of the simultaneous profiling included in Phase 1.

1.3 Personnel Involved

The three FVON Phase 1 intercomparison campaigns in Italy, the USA, and Japan, involved numerous researchers and technical operators working toward the established goals:

Italy (National Research Council, Institute for Marine Biological Resources and Biotechnologies - CNR-IRBIM, Ancona⁵)

- Michela Martinelli
- Pierluigi Penna
- Enrico Cecapolli
- Giordano Giuliani
- Filippo Domenichetti
- Piero Polidori

USA (Commercial Fisheries Research Foundation - CFRF⁶ / Ocean Data Network - ODN⁷)

- Linus Stoltz
- Carles Castro Muniain
- Cooper Van Vranken

⁵ <https://www.irbim.cnr.it/en/>

⁶ <https://www.cfrfoundation.org/>

⁷ <https://www.oceandata.net/>

Japan (Faculty of Fisheries, Nagasaki University⁸)

- Tetsutaro Takikawa
- Takahiro Tanaka
- Fuki Kudo
- Kaede Kohama
- Katsuya Takiguchi

2. Instruments to be Tested

The following compact instruments (see Table 1 for technical specifications) were evaluated during FVON Phase 1 intercomparison study across the three testing sites:

- ZebraTech **Moana TD200** and **TD1000**
- Star Oddi **Starmon TD 100m**
- JFE Advantech **Tegaru CTD ACTDf-BT** and **Tegaru CTD ACTDf5-BT**
- NKE **WiSens CTD 300**
- NKE **WiSens TD- DO 300m** and **WiSens TD-Chl-a 300m**
- Lowell **TDO profiling data logger**
- Catchcam **SeaSensor**

Instruments were available at each testing site as documented below:

- 2 JFE Advantech Tegaru CTD instruments were already available in Japan
- 2 JFE Advantech Tegaru CTD instruments were received in Italy by CNR on 23 December 2024
- 1 Tegaru CTD was provided courtesy of JFE Advantech at the same time for the USA test
- 1 NKE Wisens CTD instrument was received in Italy by CNR on 13 March 2025, this was then sent back to NKE in May and after checking of calibration, it was sent in June in Japan to Nagasaki University
- 2 NKE WiSens (DO and Chl-a) sample instruments were already available at ODN for the USA test
- 1 ZebraTech Moana TD200 instrument was received in Italy by CNR on 9 April 2025
- 1 ZebraTech Moana TD1000 instrument was received in Japan by University of Nagasaki on 1 April 2025
- 2 Moana TD200 were provided by ZebraTech for the USA test
- 2 TDO were provided courtesy of Lowell Instruments for the USA test
- 2 Star Oddi Starmon instruments were received in Italy by CNR on 24 February 2025

⁸ https://www.fe.nagasaki-u.ac.jp/suikan_e/index.html

- 1 CatchCam prototype SeaSensor was provided courtesy of CatchCam for the USA test

Each instrument was tested alongside a reference CTD instrument:

- **Seabird SBE 911plus** for the Italian and Japanese tests.
- **RBR concerto³ C.T.D|fast8** for the USA test.

The specific settings chosen for the intercomparison experiment to achieve the best possible data collection (also in relation to the suitability of the instruments for use on fishing gears) and a sufficient amount of recorded data to compare (e.g., lowest sampling interval) are listed in Table 2. Table 3 contains information about data format and user interface for each brand of instrument tested.

In Phase 1.3, an extensive statistical analysis was conducted only on data collected by instruments already on the market and collected by instruments recently calibrated by the manufacturer (to avoid interference from possible drift caused by the sensor's previous operational use). In any case, feedback regarding Phase 1.1 was provided directly (and through previous versions of the present document) to the companies.

Table 1. Technical specification obtained from the data sheets of the instruments tested during Phase 1 of the FVON intercomparison experiment carried out in the three selected regions.

PARTNER testing	CNR, Nagasaki University	CFRF/ODN	CNR, Nagasaki University	CFRF/ODN	CFRF/ODN	CFRF/ODN	CFRF/ODN	Nagasaki University	CNR, CFRF/ODN	CNR	CNR	CNR, Nagasaki University, CFRF/ODN	CNR, Nagasaki University
Region	Italy, Japan	USA	Italy, Japan	USA	USA	USA	USA	Japan	Italy, USA	Italy	Italy	Italy, Japan, USA	Italy, Japan
	Reference equipment		Instruments to test										
PRODUCER	Seabird	RBR	NKE			Lowell Instruments	CatchCam Technologies	ZebraTech		Star Oddi	JFE Advantech		
MODEL	SBE 911plus	RBR concerto³ C.T.D fast8	WiSens CTD 300	WiSen s TD- DO 300m	WiSens TD-Chl-a 300m	TDO profiling data logger 300m	SeaSensor	Moana TD1000	Moana TD200	Starmon 100m	TegarU CTD ACTDf-BT (300 m)	TegarU CTD ACTDf5-BT (600 m)	
Serial number	1419 T, 1090 C and 0308 P (Italy), 7005 (T), 6439 (C) (Japan)	205225	59F3	5dc4	61b8	2412757, 2412758	Prototype	1206 (Japan)	1064 (Italy), 794 and 800 (USA)	D0399, D0398	0BG1008 (Italy), 0BWX011 (Japan), 0GFN009 (USA)	0GFN008 (Italy), 0FVB009 (Japan)	
Size			315 mm x Ø 40 mm 435 gr in air	220 x Ø45 mm 393 gr in air	220mm X Ø 45mm, 377 g in air	178 mm x Ø 51 mm, 272 g in air	70 x 70 x 163mm with 100 x 100 x 187mm fishing mounting enclosure	145mm X Ø 40mm		197mm x Ø 40mm, 608 g in air	170mm X Ø70mm, 0.9 kg in air		
Data transmission (see also Table 3)	Manual download	Manual download	WiFi communication			Bluetooth communication	Bluetooth communication	Bluetooth communication		USB 2.0 cable	Bluetooth communication		

Power supply	Battery (Italy), Armored cable (Japan)	Battery	User-replaceable lithium battery		User-replaceable AA battery	Rechargeable Li-Ion battery	Lithium Thionyl Chloride battery, factory replacement only		Battery; chargeable via USB cable	Rechargeable Lithium-Ion Battery (wireless charging)	
Response time (s)	Conductivity & Temperature 0.065 sec; Pressure 0.015 sec	Conductivity C Temperature <0.1 sec; Pressure <0.01 sec	Temperature < 1 s		Temperature 1 second time constant	1 s in 0.5 m/s flow; 2 s in still water	Temperature 1 second time constant		Temperature 2 s (63%)	Pressure <0.1 s, Temperature <0.2 s, Conductivity <0.2 s, Salinity <0.2 s (63%)	
Temperature range(°C)	-2 to +35	-5 to +35	-2 to +35		-2 to +35	-40 to +125	-3 to +36		-2 to +40	-3 to +45	
Temperature accuracy(°C)	±0.001	±0.002	±0.005		± 0.1 (tested) (± 0.01 optional)	±0.1	±0.05		±0.025	±0.2	
Resolution	0.0002	0.00005			0.001	0.01	0.001		0.002°C (0.004°F)		
Depth range (m)	0-6800	0-500	0-300		0-300 (750m optional)	300m and 800m variants	0-1000	0-200	0-200	0-200	0-300 (750m optional)
Depth accuracy (%f.s.)	± 0.015%	± 0.05%	± 0.15%		±0.5% (0.25% optional)	±500 mbar (5.1 m)	± 0.5%		± 0.3%	±1%	
Depth Resolution	± 0.001% FS	± 0.001% FS			0.001 dBar	3 mbar (3 cm)	0.1 m		0.005% FS		
Salinity range			2-42 PSU							2-42 PSU	
Salinity accuracy			0.1 PSU								
Resolution											
Conductivity range	0-7 S/m	0-8.5 S/m	0-70 mS/cm							0.5-70 mS/cm	
Conductivity accuracy	± 0.0003%	± 0.003%	0.04 mS/cm							±0.2mS/cm	
Resolution	0.00004	0.0001									

Additional parameter(s)				Dissolved Oxygen, Turbidity	Chlorophyll a	X, Y, Z Accelerometer Based Static Orientation (0 - 360°)	turbidity, light intensity, immersion, and motion				X, Y, Z Accelerometer Based Static Orientation (0 - 360°)
Data acquisition rate	Sampling Speed 24 Hz (24 samples/sec)	Sampling Speed 8 Hz (8 samples/sec)	from 1 s to 99 hrs			1 Hz when profiling		The sampling algorithm attempts to measure every meter profiling with a maximum sampling of 1 Hz. When depth is stable, measurements are taken at a configurable interval.	from 1 s to hours	Sampling frequency 10Hz, 0.1s	
Last calibration	Italy 2023 (SBE declares drift of less than 0.001 °C every six-month), Japan January 2025	2024	Directly calibrated from the factory just before these tests.	Previously on a trawler and not recalibrated.	Calibration over a year old, but instrument never deployed	Directly calibrated from the factory just before these tests.	Directly calibrated from the factory.	Directly calibrated from the factory just before these tests.	Directly calibrated from the factory just before these tests.	Directly calibrated from the factory just before these tests.	
Link	https://www.seabird.com/sbe-911plus-ctd/product?id=60761421595	https://rbr-global.com/products/standard-loggers/rbrduo-ct/	https://nke-instrumentation.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/Datasheet_WiSens-CTD.pdf	https://nautilos-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/05/V4_WiSens-TD-DO.pdf	https://nautilos-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/05/V3_WiSens-TD-Chl-a-9.pdf	https://lowellinstruments.com/on-deck-data-system/tdo/	https://catchcam.tech/products/sensor/	https://www.zebra-tech.co.nz/moana-td/	https://www.staroddi.com/products/data-loggers/time-depth-recorder-tdr-starmon	https://www.jfe-advantech.co.jp/eng/products/ocean-tegaru-ctd.html	
Notes for deployment								Moana's firmware was specifically modified by the manufacturer for the intercomparison tests and configured to record every 5 seconds up to a depth of 200 m, and every 4 m of depth change, or 5 minutes beyond this depth.	recharge before multiple deployments, needs to be manually turned on each time via computer connection	recharge before multiple deployments	

Table 2. General operational information for each instrument tested. For each category (listed as rows), both the possible settings and the settings chosen for Phase 1 of the FVON intercomparison experiment are reported.

	Instrument	SeaBird SBE 911plus	RBRconcerto	NKE WiSens CTD	NKE Wisens DO and Chl-a	Lowell TDO	CatchCam SeaSensor	ZebraTech TD200 and TD 1000	Star Oddi Starmon	JFE Advantech Tegarú CTD
Country		Italy, Japan	USA	Italy, Japan	USA	USA	USA	Italy, Japan, USA	Italy	Italy, Japan, USA
Time Setting	Possible settings	Time derived from the instrument's acquisition system (UTC)	Time derived from the instrument's acquisition system (UTC)	Configurable via app, can select any time		UTC from Deck Data Hub	UTC	UTC - No manual setting	The logger synchronizes its internal clock with the date & time on the PC being used to configure it	Syncs with phone via app
	Setting used	UTC	UTC	CEST (GMT +2; Italy), JST (GMT +9; Japan)	EDT (Summer: UTC -4)	UTC	UTC	UTC	CEST (GMT +2)	CEST (GMT +2; Italy), JST (GMT +9; Japan), EDT (Summer UTC -4; USA)
Units Setting	Possible settings	Not changeable	Not changeable	Not changeable via app		Not changeable	Configurable via App	Not changeable via app, possibly from deck unit	Changeable via app (Settings > Preferences > Units)	Not changeable via app
	Setting used	Pressure: db; Depth: m; Temperature: deg C; Conductivity: S/m; Salinity: PSU; Oxygen: ml/l; Oxygen: % saturation	Pressure: db; Depth: m; Temperature: deg C; Conductivity: mS/cm; Salinity: PSU;	Pressure: bar; Temperature: Celsius degrees; Conductivity: mS/cm; Practical salinity: PSU; Depth: meters	Pressure: bar; Temperature: Celsius degrees; Depth: meters	Pressure: dbar; Temperature: Celsius; Accelerometer: Raw Counts 256 per g	Temperature: Celsius degrees; Depth: meters	Depth units are dBar, Temperature: Degree Centigrade	Temperature: Celsius degrees; Depth: meters	Depth: meters; Pressure: MPa, Temperature: Celsius degree; Salinity, Cond: mS/cm

Sampling Interval	Possible settings	Software programmable	Software programmable	Sampling regime configurable at: continuous or fishing (allows to set 2 different sampling intervals); sampling interval: from 1 sec to 99 hrs	Sampling regime configurable at: continuous or fishing (allows to set 2 different sampling intervals); sampling interval: from 2 sec to 99 hrs	Two modes: 1) Configurable from 1/s to 1/hour 2) Adaptable and configurable based on depth. From 1 Hz to 1 hour. Typically 1 min when depth is stable, 1 Hz when profiling..	Programmable from 2 s to 1 hour	Factory configuration only allows to record every 5 sec until 200m, then every 4m/5min	Programmable	Factory configuration only allows to record every 0.1 sec below 2m depth
	Setting used	1/24 sec	1/8 sec	Sampling regime continuous, sampling interval 1 sec (except for some casts in Japan where the averaging function was trialed, see below)	Sampling regime continuous, sampling interval 2 sec	1 second when profiling, 2 seconds when static	15 seconds	Factory configuration	Set to record every 1 sec	Factory configuration
How to Turn On/Off	Possible settings	Via Deck Unit	Via Ruskin App and twist cap activation	Manually through a magnet (there is also an on/off button visible in the app that needs to be set to on)		Via Deck Unit. Unit automatically reduces recording rate when on the surface		On/off on condition automatically turns on below 1 m depth	Manually through computer connected via USB 2.0 Standard-B plug	Manually through a magnet
	Setting used	Via Deck Unit	Via Ruskin App	Magnet		Deck Unit		Instrument put underwater	Via computer	Magnet
How to Start/Stop recording	Possible settings	Use the software to send the necessary commands to start logging according to Sea-Bird Scientific's training modules.	Via Ruskin App or using twist activation	Manual or programmable (based on pressure)		Automatically starts recording when submerged.	Starts/stops based on immersion sensor	On condition: Automatically starts recording below 1 m depth	Starts at the time scheduled during the laptop configuration (with minimum 5 min delay after setting)	On condition: automatically starts recording below 1 m depth
	Setting used	Start and stop via patent software, CTD connected through cable allowing to see the real depth	Twist activation just prior to instrument deployment	On condition: Start acquisition with pressure >0.1 bar; end acquisition with pressure <0.2 bar	On condition: Start with pressure >0.2 bar; end with pressure <0.1 bar	Automatic	Automatic	Automatic	Start at the time scheduled during the laptop configuration (after 5 min)	Automatic

Table 3. Data format and user interface information for each brand of instrument tested.

Instrument	NKE WiSens CTD, DO and Chl-a	Lowell TDO	CatchCam SeaSensor	ZebraTech TD200 and TD 1000	Star Oddi Starmon	JFE Advantech Tegarú CTD
Dedicated app	Yes; Mobile, via Wi-Fi	Yes; Linux via Bluetooth. In development; Mobile via Bluetooth	Yes; Mobile, via Bluetooth	Yes; Mobile, via Bluetooth	Yes; PC, via cable	Yes; Mobile, via Bluetooth
Dedicated Deck Unit Availability	Yes	Yes (deck unit open-source compatible with other instruments)	No	Yes	No	No
Compatible with other deck units?	No	Potentially, Bluetooth data transfer protocols are open source to permit use by other deck units	No	Proprietary Bluetooth protocols have been successfully integrated into the open source Lowell Instruments Deck Data Hub but are not widely available for integration into other deck units	No	No
Data format	CSV/ZIP	CSV, binary .lid file for backup	CSV	CSV	Xlsx	Raw file in zip folder (open as txt)/CSV
Data-file structure	One file every cast	One file every download (typically every cast)	One file every cast	One file every cast	One file every cast	One file every cast
Mean file size	about 25 KB for a 15 min cast in the USA (440 data points), about 200 for a 60 min cast in Italy (3900 data points)	28 KB for a 20 min cast in the USA (600 data points)	about 10 KB for a 15 min cast in the USA (65 data points)	12 KB for a 15 min cast in the USA (about 220 data points), 20 for about 50 min cast in Italy (600 data points)	about 200 KB for a 60 min cast in Italy (3600 data points)	about 600 KB for a 20 min cast in the USA (10000 data points), about 1.5 MB for a 45 min cast in Italy (27000 data points)
How to delete data	Via App (16Mb memory capacity)	Data automatically deleted when successfully offloaded (128 MB memory capacity, approximately 12 million samples)	Data marked for overwriting when downloaded to App.	Data automatically deleted when offloaded by app or deck unit (31146 records memory capacity)	Via computer software: older data is erased from memory when new settings are sent to the recorder	Overwrite data when memory is full (128MB)

3. Cruise Details

3.1 Italy (Central Adriatic Sea, May 2025)

The Task Team agreed that the first test site would be in Italy. Agreements were then reached with instrument manufacturers willing to participate in the tests to ship the instruments to Italy. In the meantime, the personnel from the Institute for Marine Biological Resources and Biotechnology of the Italian National Research Council (CNR-IRBIM) carried out the preparatory work necessary to hold a single-day testing cruise entirely dedicated to FVON activities, which eventually occurred on 12 May 2025 in the Central Adriatic Sea (Figure 2). The testing was carried out on board the R/V (Research Vessel) *Tecnopesca II* provided by CNR-IRBIM in kind for FVON activities. The 16-meter vessel is equipped with a Geographic Positioning System (GPS) antenna, a multibeam echo sounder, a professional winch, and a fixed crane for handling heavy instruments such as the CTD frame.

Figure 2. Map of the Central Adriatic Sea. The lines represent the bathymetry in the area. The star indicates the location of the selected sampling station. The box in the top right shows the position of the study area within the Mediterranean basin.

As chair of the FVON Instrument Intercomparison Study Task Team, Michela Martinelli was the contact point for instrument manufacturers, led preliminary planning work, and coordinated the tests carried out in Italy with the help of Pierluigi Penna. Pierluigi and Enrico Cecapolli performed an initial evaluation of the instruments' functionality and settings before field testing with the help of Fillippo Domenichetti. Giordano Giuliani oversaw the positioning and assembly of instruments on the support structure (i.e., the CTD frame). Enrico prepared and carried out the cruise with assistance from Filippo, Giordano, and Piero Polidori. Enrico and Michela downloaded the data, drafted the present document, and carried out some preliminary analyses.

Tested instruments included: WiSens CTD 300 m produced by NKE Instrumentation, Moana TD200 produced by ZebraTech, 2 Starmon TD 100m by Star-Oddi, one Tegarú CTD ACTDf-BT and one Tegarú ACTDf5-BT by JFE Advantech. Table 1 summarizes the main technical features of the instruments, while Table 2 describes the operational settings available for their deployment. Before mounting the instruments on the CTD frame, each unit was tested individually in the port area of Ancona to verify basic functionality and allow the team to gain familiarity with their operation. Data collected in these preliminary tests were downloaded and inspected.

All the instruments tested were mounted on the SeaBird 911 CTD frame (Figure 3). Instruments were positioned and oriented so that their depth detector sat at the same height as the CTD's reference depth detector to minimize depth-related biases in the measurements. The specific settings (e.g., lowest sampling interval) for the intercomparison experiment were chosen to maximize data acquisition mimicking use on fishing gears, and obtain a sufficient amount of recorded data to compare. These settings are listed in Table 2.

CTD cast replicas were performed in a single station located in the Central Adriatic Sea (latitude: 43.829N, longitude: 13.713E; Figure 2). The maximum depth recorded in the selected station was 70.2 meters. Five CTD casts were carried out (Figure 4), ensuring at least 3 valid hauls for each of the instruments tested.

In accordance with the previously defined protocol, each CTD cast included stops at 7 depth quotas (10 m, 20 m, 40 m, and 60 m during the downcast, 40 m, 20 m, and 10 m during the upcast), selected on the basis of the maximum depth of the station. Each stop lasted around 5 minutes. The duration was selected to ensure reliable data collection and to provide a sufficient number of measurements for analysis, taking into account that some instruments require several seconds to stabilize at each depth. In total, each cast lasted around 50 minutes from the deployment of the CTD frame to its retrieval back into the boat.

Figure 3. Overview of the instruments mounted on the SeaBird 911 CTD frame. Each instrument is indicated by a red arrow. The blue lines highlight the position of the instruments at the same height as the CTD depth detector (red circle).

Figure 4. A) Deploying operations carried out by the CNR-IRBIM personnel in the Central Adriatic Sea during the intercomparison experiment. B) CTD frame equipped with all the instruments involved in the test deployed from the R/V *Tecnopeca II* during the intercomparison experiment.

3.2 USA (Mid-Atlantic Bight, June 2025)

The Commercial Fisheries Research Foundation (CFRF) conducted the USA test in tandem with their regularly scheduled ventless trap survey work in South Fork Wind Farm (Figure 5). The F/V (Fishing Vessel) *Amelia Ann* conducted the test in the wind energy lease area on 11 June 2025 using the pot hauler for raising the CTD cage with test instruments affixed to the outside.

Figure 5. Map of the Mid-Atlantic Bight. The lines represent the bathymetry in the area. The star indicates the location of the selected sampling station. The box on top-right shows the position of the study area along the eastern seaboard of North America.

Cooper Van Vranken (FVON co-chair) coordinated the test carried out in the USA under the guidance of Michela Martinelli. Linus Stoltz (CFRF) conducted the testing aboard the F/V *Amelia Ann*. Carles Castro Muniain (ODN) led data processing under the guidance of Linus, Cooper, and Michela.

Tested instruments included: one WiSens TD-DO 300m and one WiSens TD-Chl-a 300m both produced by NKE Instrumentation, two Moana TD200 (200m) produced by ZebraTech, 2 TDO data loggers 300m by Lowell Instruments, one Tegar ACTDf5-BT 200m by JFE Advantech and one SeaSensor prototype produced by CatchCam. Table 1 summarizes the main technical features of the instruments. Before mounting the instruments on the CTD frame, each unit was tested individually in the port area to verify basic functionality and allow the team to become familiar with their use. Data collected in these preliminary tests were downloaded and inspected.

All instruments were then mounted on the RBR *concerto* CTD frame (Figure 6). The specific settings selected are listed in Table 2. The vertical offsets of the pressure instruments relative to the reference CTD pressure instrument were recorded and are reported in Table 4.

Figure 6. Overview of the instruments mounted on the RBR *concerto* CTD frame. Each instrument is indicated by a red arrow.

Table 4. Mounting height offsets from the RBR reference CTD for trialed instruments.

Instrument	Direction	Offset (cm)
ZebraTech moana TD200 (2)	plus	4.4
Lowell TDO (2)	plus	17.8
NKE WiSens TD-DO and TD-Chl-a	plus	9.9
JFE Advantech Tegarū	minus	17.8
CatchCam SeaSensor	minus	6.07

CTD cast replicas were performed in a single station located in the Mid-Atlantic Bight (latitude: 49.294N, longitude: 71.050W; Figure 5). The maximum depth was approximately 40 meters. During the test, one CTD cast was carried out following the established protocol (Figure 7).

The CTD cast included stops at roughly 5-meter intervals on the downcast but did not stop on the upcast. Each stop lasted about 2 minutes. In total, the cast lasted around 15 minutes from deployment of the CTD frame to its retrieval back in the boat.

Figure 7. LEFT) Deploying operations for the intercomparison experiment carried out by the CFRF and Captain Greg and Deckhand Andrew in the Mid-Atlantic Bight. RIGHT) CTD frame equipped with all the instruments involved in the test on the deck of the F/V *Amelia Ann* during the intercomparison experiment.

3.3 Japan (Tsushima Strait & Goto Basin, June-July 2025)

The Japanese test was divided in two different legs:

[Voy. 1026] Departure: 14:36 JST, 25 June

 Arrival: 08:55 JST, 27 June

[Voy. 1028] Departure: 14:22 JST, 2 July

 Arrival: 07:57 JST, 4 July

The instruments were attached to the frame of the SBE911plus-CTD for testing and included:

1. Tegarū CTD, JFE Advantech:
 - a. ACTDf-BT, Pressure resistance 300 m, Voy. 1028 only
 - b. ACTDf5-BT, Pressure resistance 600 m
2. WiSens CTD, NKE, Pressure resistance 300 m
3. Moana TD1000, ZebraTech. Pressure rating 1000 m.

All instruments were installed at the same height as the SBE instrument (Figure 8). Figure 9 shows the top schematic views of the relative position of each instrument. CTD vertical observations were carried out with a winch speed of about 1 m/s (or 0.5 m/s experimentally). The ship's track and observation points are shown in Figure 10.

Figure 8. The instruments installed on the CTD frame of the T/S (Training Ship) *Kakuyo-maru* (**a**: Voy. 1026, **b**: deep casts of Voy. 1028, **c**: operator analysing the CTD casts, **d**: shallow casts of Voy. 1028). The rosette water samplers were attached to the frame during Voy. 1026 but were removed during Voy. 1028. Photo **c** shows the dry lab in the T/S *Kakuyo-maru*.

Figure 9. Schematic views of the instrument arrangements from above. Red indicates the positions of each instrument. The diameter of the outer circle frame (bold line) is approximately 1 m.

Figure 10. Ship track (red line) and observation points (blue dots). Thin and thick contour lines indicate the bathymetry every 25 m (less than 200 m depth) and 250 m, respectively.

CTD observations were conducted on 26 June in the western channel of the Tsushima Straits during Voy. 1026 (Figure 10). The observation line is along the Tsushima Trough with a maximum depth of approximately 200 m, where cold water exists at the lowest layer. Following the earlier intercomparison observations made in Italy, the CTD observations were attempted by stopping the winch for 5 minutes at several depths at the station W00 shown in Figure 10. However, due to strong currents (more than 1 knot), the armored cable tilted significantly and could not maintain a constant depth. Three casts (W00_1, W00_2, and W00_3) were conducted in Voy. 1026, in which the winch was stopped on its downcast when it reached depths of 30 (or 10), 50, 100, and 200 m. After that, normal CTD observations were conducted from W00 to W11, the southern end of the trough (Figure 10), without stopping the winch. An additional observation at station W12, located farther south and approximately 130 m deep, was included to complement the W11 measurement.

During Voy. 1028, CTD observations were conducted on 3 July in the Goto Submarine Canyon and the Danjo Basin (Figure 10). These areas are deeper than the Tsushima Straits. Due to limited wire length, observations were restricted to a maximum depth of approximately 500 m. In the submarine canyon, a CTD vertical section was obtained from 11 stations (G1 to G5) using SBE9p-CTD, ACTDf5-BT, and TD1000 (Figures 8b and 9). The deepest point along the observation line reaches approximately 560 m. Following the section observation, the additional instruments (ACTDf-BT and WiSens) were mounted on the SBE9p-CTD frame, and eight CTD casts were conducted at station G2b (Figures 8d and 9). In four of these casts, the winch speed was set to 1 m/s or 0.5 m/s, and the averaging function of the WiSens was alternately activated or deactivated. In the remaining four casts, the CTD winch was paused at certain depths (30, 50, 100, and 200 m) during both the downcast and upcast. Subsequently, four additional CTD casts were carried out at station TT1 (water depth ~700 m) in the Danjo Basin, using SBE9p-CTD, ACTDf5-BT, and TD1000. In three of these casts, the CTD winch was paused at selected depths (100, 200, 300 m, and maximum wire length) during both the downcast and upcast.

Table 5 summarizes the deployment methods and instruments tested at each CTD station.

Table 5. Stations list with remarks.

Station	Remarks	NKE WiSens	JFE Tegar600	JFE Tegar300	ZebraTech Moana TD-1000
W00_1	Stop 5 min at 10, 50, 100, 200 of downcast	yes	yes		yes
W00_2	Stop 5 min at 30, 50, 100, 200 of downcast	yes	yes		yes
W00_3	Stop 5 min at 30, 50, 100, 200 of downcast	yes	yes		yes
W00		yes	yes		yes
W01		yes	yes		yes
W02		yes	yes		yes
W03		yes	yes		yes
W04		yes	yes		yes
W05		yes	yes		yes
W06		yes	yes		yes
W07		yes	yes		yes
W08		yes	yes		yes
W09		yes	yes		yes
W10		yes	yes		yes
W11		yes	yes		yes
W12		yes	yes		yes
G1			yes		yes
G1b			yes		yes
G2			yes		yes
G2a			yes		yes
G2b			yes		yes
G3			yes		yes
G3a			yes		yes
G3b			yes		yes
G4			yes		yes
G4a			yes		yes
G5			yes		yes
G2b_1	Winch speed: 0.5 m/s	yes	yes	yes	yes
G2b_2	Winch speed: 0.5 m/s	yes, averaging mode: 16 sec	yes	yes	yes
G2b_3	Winch speed: 1 m/s	yes, averaging mode: 16 sec	yes	yes	yes
G2b_4	Winch speed: 1 m/s	yes	yes	yes	yes
G2b_5	Stop 5 min at 30, 50, 100, 200 of down/up cast	Memory over	yes	yes	yes
G2b_6	Stop 5 min at 30, 50, 100, 200 of down/up cast	yes	yes	yes	yes
G2b_7	Stop 5 min at 30, 50, 100, 200 of down/up cast	yes	yes	yes	yes
G2b_8	Stop 5 min at 30, 50, 100, 200 of down/up cast	Data deleted by mistake	yes	yes	yes
TT1_1	Stop 5 min at 100, 200, 300, max of down/up cast		yes		yes
TT1_2	Stop 5 min at 100, 200, 300, max of down/up cast		yes		yes
TT1_3	Stop 5 min at 100, 200, 300, max of down/up cast		yes		yes
TT1_4			yes		yes

4. Preliminary Results and Notes from the Various Teams

The three Phase 1 intercomparison campaigns, performed independently by each regional team, provided distinct perspectives on instrument performance under different environmental conditions, vessel configurations, and technical expertise. The feedback collected also informed direct responses from the manufacturers, who delivered comments and planned possible improvements ahead of Phase 2 testing.

4.1 Measurement Performance

This section assesses functional comparability and profiling capability, not formal accuracy metrics. For bias, offset magnitude, and uncertainty quantification, see the companion analytical documentation.

All tested compact instruments produced vertical temperature profiles to be compared with reference CTDs across Italy, the USA, and Japan.

In general, no major issues occurred during the intercomparison experiment carried out in Italy. However, some technical drawbacks related to the instrument settings caused incomplete data collection for some instruments (see sections below). Figure 11 shows an example of depth and temperature profiles obtained simultaneously by the tested instruments in one of the CTD cast replicas performed in the Adriatic Sea.

As an example, Figure 12 displays one of the outputs obtained for the Italian cruise through the R script developed in Phase 1.3; this illustrates all the depth profiles collected by the various tested instruments together and the identified stable depth intervals on which further analyses were carried out. More details on the definition of stable depths for each cruise and statistical results can be found in the script and accompanying data analysis documentation.

Figure 11. Example of depth (in meters) and temperature (in degrees Celsius) profiles obtained from a cast performed during the intercomparison experiment in the Adriatic Sea.

Figure 12. Depth profiles collected by all tested instruments (top panel) during the Adriatic Sea cruise and identified stable depth intervals (bottom panel).

In general, no major issue occurred during the instrument intercomparison experiment carried out in the Mid-Atlantic. However, several operational challenges and notable instrument features were identified which would impact suitability for FVON deployments (see sections below). Figure 13 shows an example of depth and temperature profiles obtained simultaneously with the reference CTD by the instruments tested in the USA.

Figure 13. The depth (in meters) and temperature (in degrees Celsius) profile obtained from a cast performed during the intercomparison experiment in the Mid-Atlantic Bight.

In Japan, cold bottom water was observed at station W11 shallower than 160 m. Cold bottom water was not observed at station W12, as demonstrated by the vertical profiles of temperature and salinity measured at cast W00_1 and shown in Figures 14 and 15, respectively. There was a sharp thermocline above the bottom layer of cold water. These data could also be useful to verify the response time of the instruments.

Figure 14. Temperature profiles at W00_1. The winch speed was about 1 m/s.

Figure 15. Salinity profiles at W00_1. The winch speed was about 1 m/s.

Representative vertical profiles of temperature and salinity from cast G2b_1 are shown in Figures 16 and 17, respectively.

Figure 16. Temperature profiles at G2b_1. The winch speed was about 0.5 m/s.

Figure 17. Salinity profiles at G2b_1. The winch speed was about 0.5 m/s.

4.2 Set up and Ease of Use

Overall, teams achieved better results when using instruments with which they were familiar. The team in Italy is most familiar with NKE, the team in the USA is experienced with ZebraTech and Lowell Instruments, and the Japan team regularly uses JFE.

Table 2 describes in detail the customization level offered by each tested instrument for data recording, and the settings used by the 3 teams.

Setup and customization is crucial to operational reliability. A large number of settings and customization available for instruments can be both advantageous and problematic depending on operator experience. While extensive customization supports a wide variety of applications, it also increases the potential for configuration errors.

As an example, no particular issues were encountered with the NKE WiSens instrument during setup in Italy. On the other end in the USA, the NKE WiSens instruments missed the upper part of the test cast because the pressure threshold for initiating recordings had been set too deep due to confusion with pressure units.

The ZebraTech Moana instrument offers limited configuration options and automatically initiates data recording below 1 m depth. Nevertheless, in Italy it failed to activate during the second cast, leading to a loss of data. Subsequently, the producer clarified that the issue likely originated from app workflow. After offloading data, the user must press the “disconnect” button, otherwise the instrument remains connected and does not properly enter the sampling mode. When paired with the deck unit during fishing operations, seamless data transfer upon recovery should be guaranteed, preventing this problem.

JFE Advantech Tegarú instruments largely function automatically and were found to be intuitive. However, the JFE isow app works best when launched and synchronized with the instrument at the beginning of each observing session, requiring more responsibility from the operator.

StarOddi Starmon relies on a more complex user interface, and the setup procedure proved to be more complex and less intuitive than for the other instruments, requiring manual activation before each cast (a “multiple cast” option is available but only enables recording at predetermined time intervals). As a result, the first two casts were not recorded due to an incorrect instrument setup.

4.3 Data Download and Transmission

As illustrated in Table 3, several instruments support both manual data retrieval (e.g. through dedicated mobile applications) and automated offloading, which also enables direct transmission to a central datacenter. Indeed, NKE WiSens, ZebraTech Moana, Lowell TDO, and JFE Advantech Tegarú instruments are all equipped with tools for automatically retrieving data from the sensors once out of water after a cast and transferring data in near real time to a data center. This automation is critical because data reliability is influenced not only by the sensor's capability but is also affected by data handling processes, and automated systems substantially reduce the burden on

operators. Furthermore, near-real-time transmission is already an established capability within several FVON programs.

Additionally, instruments such as the WiSens and Tegarú feature multiparameter capabilities, allowing for the concurrent measurement of various environmental variables at the same time (check companion documentation for details on metadata and data formats).

The ZebraTech instrument allows to check and manually download the acquired data through the dedicated ZebraTech Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) Android/iOS App. For operational use on board fishing vessels ZebraTech recommends coupling the instrument with the solar-powered Moana Deck Unit for automated offload and sending to the data center. While mounted on a fishing vessel, this enables data to be instantly downloaded from the instrument via Bluetooth upon retrieval of the gear and then transferred automatically to a data center (via on vessel satellite WiFi or cellular GSM). Similarly, NKE instruments offer the possibility to check and download data via a WiFi connection to a mobile phone and a dedicated Web App that also allows manual configuration of the sensors. NKE also provides a WiHub to be installed on board vessels to enable automatic data offloading via WiFi and near real time transmission to data centers (via GPRS). The WiHub can also be connected to other on-board systems via Ethernet connection.

Lowell Instruments TDO-1 sensors support automatic download via Bluetooth Low Energy to a Linux computer running the Lowell Instruments Deck Data Hub software.

JFE Advantech instruments pair via Bluetooth with the “isow” dedicated Android App for data visualization, download and direct cloud upload.

Star Oddi instrument provides manual data download via cable to a PC through the SeaStar software which also allows setting of the sensor.

Several issues arose during Phase 1 tests regarding data flows, mainly due to low team familiarity with the instruments in use.

Since there was no deck unit available in Italy for this testing phase, the process of downloading data manually in delayed mode from the ZebraTech Moana was found challenging, as the Bluetooth communication with the sensor is automatically turned off after a while and requires pressure increase again to reactivate Bluetooth data offload. However, where available, the dedicated ZebraTech deck unit eliminates the need for manual data download enabling data to be instantly downloaded from the instrument upon retrieval of the gear and then transferred automatically to a data center.

The choice was made in Italy to test manual download data from the NKE WiSens, through the Web App, a process which encountered no issues.

In the observations made during the Japanese tests, tablet PCs were used to connect to the instruments instead of automatic data transfer devices which were not available (i.e. the NKE “WiHub” for WiSens or the ZebraTech “deck unit” for Moana). An issue arose with the memory capacity of the NKE WiSens. The instrument’s memory reached its limit during the cruise, resulting in the loss of one dataset. Although the logger appeared to have ample remaining storage, with four test casts (~7 m) at port recorded,

the memory quickly filled during the cruise. Also in this case, if the WiHub was present during the tests carried out in Japan, there would have presumably been no issue related to data transfer to on-land servers or clouds. In case of use without the WiHub, a future firmware upgrade with an option for an auto-overwrite function could be evaluated.

The JFE Advantech Tegarū CTD enabled in Japan automatic data transfer to cloud server via the smartphone/tablet app isow (IDEA Consultants, Inc.). Data downloading was manual in Italy from the dedicated Android app "isow" for JFE Advantech Tegarū, with no major issues (check companion documentation for details on metadata and data formats).

All instruments were offloaded manually in the USA via app, with the exception of the Moana, for which a ZebraTech deck unit was used to automatically offload and collect location data. The CatchCam SeaSensor is a new offering, with an extensive suite of parameters beyond temperature. Downloading data via the dedicated mobile app proved to be straightforward.

4.4 Time and Position

All tested instruments do not directly record GPS position. The vessel's position (not the sensor's) is subsequently directly and automatically associated based on the timestamp when using deck units or hubs for NKE, ZebraTech, and Lowell.

Indeed, during the USA test, the dedicated ZebraTech Deck Unit was used to retrieve location data of the Moana instrument, as the data processing team could not join aboard the vessel during the test. However, while downloading data manually, ZebraTech BLE App also records GPS data at the time of offload.

As for the JFE Advantech Tegarū, time series positioning data can be obtained via the "isow" app, but it is necessary to receive continuous GPS signals. The app is thus best launched and synchronized with the instrument at the beginning of each observation session (rather than before every cast). Depending on the fishing boat and the situation, it may be difficult to receive GPS while charging the battery.

Not having tools implemented for near real-time observations, the only way to associate the position data from the vessel's onboard equipment with the timestamp of the instruments for StarOddi Starmon and CathCam SeaSensor would be through post-processing.

Once the different time zones used by the various instruments were aligned (see Table 2), the reference time could generally vary by a few seconds between the various instruments. However, there was a serious issue with the CatchCam SeaSensor timestamp during the USA test, which was approximately 18 minutes ahead of UTC. If SeaSensor data was stitched with GPS data from an independent source, these 18 minutes would result in geolocation errors on the scale of several kilometers. The time offset was manually corrected in the collected dataset. The timestamp offset identified during the USA test was acknowledged by the producer and traced to a firmware bug. The manufacturer is actively implementing a fix in consultation with the research team.

4.5 Power supply

For operational deployments, battery longevity and options for recharging or battery field replacement require particular attention. No outright battery failures occurred during Phase 1 testing; however, power supply management is a key differentiator depending on the presence of an operator during deployment or the direct involvement of fishermen while instruments are used on board fishing vessels.

The units tested included different types of battery systems: User-replaceable battery (NKE WiSens, Lowell TDO), factory-replaceable battery (ZebraTech Moana), or chargeable battery (CatchCam SeaSensor, Star Oddi Starmon, JFE Advantech Tegarū). The chargeable battery needs to be charged once a day (or less), whereas the user/factory replaceable systems have a long lifetime without the need to constantly monitor remaining battery power.

WiSens runs on an internal lithium battery with a relatively low drain rate that can be easily replaced on-site. The battery level can be read from the Web App or from downloaded data files. Battery consumption depends also on the selected sampling regime (details available in Martinelli et al. 2025).

Moana has an internal battery with a lifespan greater than two years, but to replace it, it must be returned to the manufacturer.

Lowell TDO use standard AA replaceable batteries with an estimated life of one year (depending on the sampling regime selected).

Long battery lives, together with the use of deck units, enable WiSens, Lowell and Moana automatic data collection on board fishing vessels without operator intervention for extended periods. These three instruments with accompanying deck units are currently in use in several FVON programs.

Tegarū battery life is shorter, but batteries can be recharged by an on-site operator. At present in fact Tegarū is used by hundreds of fishermen in Japan, directly lowered overboard and recharged as needed. Power management remains a limitation for application directly on fishing gears (i.e. not requiring operator intervention) and across diverse fishing fleets (e.g. with a lower level of involvement of fishermen), even though the wireless charging system is well suited for the conditions aboard fishing vessels.

When using applications to download the data, tablet/phone battery life proved essential. Both the JFE Advantech Tegarū app "isow" and the "AUTO-OFFLOAD MODE" of the "ZebraTech BLE" Moana app consume substantial battery power. However, the latter is not intended for operational data offload.

Starmon rechargeable battery is reported by the producer to be long-lasting. At a 1-second sampling interval, a single charge could potentially last about three months while still leaving sufficient memory capacity (it supports 8.4 million TD measurements). This could make it suitable for long periods of use on fishing gear; however, this instrument currently requires human intervention to download the data.

The CatchCam SeaSensor battery life can last for multiple days of fishing trips, and the specialized charger that does not require opening the instrument is practical to be used on board.

5 Concluding Remarks

During Phase 1, the instruments were all mounted on CTD frames to test them against reference CTDs and evaluate their baseline operational behavior. Additionally, the three testing teams also reported some observations on the suitability of the instruments for deployment on fishing gear. These considerations, together with producers' feedback and the results of the extended data analysis, will guide the selection of instruments for the initial Phase 2 deployments.

In addition to the considerations reported in the previous paragraphs, it is also important to mention that WiSens, Lowell, CatchCam, and Moana can be sold with mechanical guards or housing to protect the sensors from rough fishing environments. This, combined with long-lasting batteries and deck units for automatic data transmission for the Lowell, Moana, and WiSens, makes these three instruments suitable for automatic use directly on the fishing gear without operator intervention for extended periods (in fact, they are currently used by several FVON programs).

Based on the considerations above and the fact that the NKE WiSens instrument had to be sent back to the parent company for inspection before being sent to Japan for the subsequent FVON intercomparison test, the Italian team decided to carry out a preliminary Phase 2 trial on a commercial fishing vessel operating in the Adriatic Sea, involving only the Moana and WiSens instruments. The instruments were installed on the otter door of a bottom trawler and recorded eight fishing hauls between 18 and 19 May 2025. These datasets will be analyzed in subsequent stages of the study.

These instruments, together with the Lowell, will be the subject of further Phase 2 tests which are currently being planned to be carried out in Italy and the USA on various fishing gear during commercial fishing trips.

The Japanese team suggests that Tegarū is robust enough to also be tested on fishing gear such as bottom trawler otter doors; therefore, given its charging and data download features, it could be considered for short-duration test deployments in Phase 2.

Similarly, even if the instrument does not have a GPS tracking system, nor a platform for automatically sending data to a data center (and would thus require occasional operator intervention for data downloads), thanks to its long-lasting recording potential and the robustness of the sensor, Starmon could be trialed on fishing gear for short deployment trials, along with the other instruments.

It is also worth mentioning SeaSensor's robust protective housing, with multiple attachment points for fishing nets, which represents an innovative approach for mounting.

Phase 1 demonstrated that the instruments currently in use in the different FVON programs are operationally comparable. Furthermore, the exchanges among the Task

Team members highlighted how the entire system, including data offload and ease of use, needs to be taken into consideration. Ensuring minimal interference with fishing operations and providing feedback from fishermen are critical factors for successful FVON deployments, which will be hopefully further evaluated in Phase 2.

The Task Team's opportunities to carry out Phase 2 testing will depend on several factors including but not limited to the availability of fishermen to host multiple sensors at the same time. Phase 2 testing may also be a useful opportunity to test additional relevant aspects such as fouling, handling, and protection against harsh conditions during long-term deployments on different fishing gear. Further analysis could be conducted on the operational burden of battery life, data offload, and deployment configuration requirements for fishermen.

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